

IMPACT OF FARMER'S SOCIAL STATUS IN THE CULTIVATION OF JASMINE FLOWERS: SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DINDIGUL DISTRICT

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Introduction:

As in the case of any other agricultural activity, the cultivation of jasmine require manpower to perform cultivation activities like weeding, tilling, application of manure, watering and harvesting. Social status plays an important role to per the above said activities.

Statement of the Problem: Cultivation of jasmine flowers is a lucrative business to the cultivators. This is an important crop which helps to increase the social status of the jasmine cultivators.

Scope of the Study: The present study to examines the opinion of the jasmine cultivators in Dindigul district only.

Objective of the Study: To study role of social status of the sample Jasmine flowers cultivators in Dindigul district

Sample Size: Researcher randomly selected 300 farmers as sample in order to carry this study.

Sources of Data: This study is largely based on the primary data, because, the information relating to the study is extremely scant. Required primary data were collected in the course of interview with the farmers through survey method

Tools and Techniques Used:

- ✓ More specifically, to understand the relative share of various distributions in a variable, the percentage method has been used.
- ✓ Multiple regression technique used to find out the simultaneous effects of the independent variables on the dependent variables.
- ✓ Chi-Square test helps to decide whether there is association between two variables or not.

Analysis and Interpretations:

1. Percent:

Age: Age is an important factor in determining the preference for cultivation of Jasmine. Since the cultivation of Jasmine requires a continuous monitoring and also a long-term gestation period, the young and the middle-aged are expected to cultivate Jasmine rather than the old-aged. Hence, it becomes pertinent to understand the distribution of age of the sample Jasmine cultivators.

Table 1: Distribution of sample cultivators by age

S.No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Up to 30	8	2.67
2	31-40	5	1.67
3	41-50	150	50.00
4	51-60	65	21.67
5	61 and above	72	24.00
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that 50 per cent of the sample respondents are in the age group of 41 – 50 years. 24 per cent are in the age group of 61 years and above. There are 21.67 per cent of respondents who are in the age group of 51 – 60 years. While 3.00 per cent are up to the age of 30 years and the remaining 2.40 per cent are in the age group of up to 30 years. Thus, from the analysis it can be concluded that majority (50%) of the sample respondents are in the age group of 41 – 50 years.

Gender: The distribution of gender is an important factor determining the active roleplayed in the flower cultivation. In the Indian context, while practicing agriculture, certain work which involves heavy labour is being carried out by men while the light work is being taken up by women. However, it is difficult to practice agriculture fully by women. In the present paragraph it is attempted to understand the gender of the Jasmine cultivators.

Table 2: Distribution of sample cultivators by gender

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Male	218	72.67
2	Female	82	27.33

	Total	300	100.00
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Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that 72.67 per cent of the sample respondents are male while the remaining 27.33 per cent are female. Thus, from the analysis it can be concluded that majority (72.67%) of the sample respondents are male.

Educational Qualification: Education is an important factor determining the ability to understand the agricultural schemes of the government, a knowledge on floricultural practices, importance of attending the required extension program and above all in understanding the marketing situation. Hence, in the present paragraph it is attempted to examine the education attainment of the sample Jasmine cultivators. The following table expresses the educational attainment of the Jasmine cultivators.

Table 3: Distribution of sample cultivators by educational qualification

S.No	Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Illiterates	114	38.00
2	Primary	35	11.67
3	Middle	80	26.67
4	10th	40	13.33
5	+ 2 and above	31	10.33
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table expresses that 38 per cent of the sample respondents are illiterates. 26.67 per cent of them have completed middle level education. While 13.33 per cent of the sample respondents are educated up to X standard, 11.67 per cent of them have completed primary level of education. The remaining 10.33 per cent of them have completed higher secondary and above level of education. Thus, from the above analysis it can be concluded that majority (38%) of the sample Jasmine cultivators are illiterates.

Marital Status: The marital status is another important factor determining the active participation in the cultivation of agricultural produce. Generally in the Indian social set-up, the married women have the major additional responsibility of household activities rather than the male members and hence it is expected that the time available to the women-headed household is comparatively less than their counterpart who can spend higher time in floricultural activities. Hence, in the present paragraph it is attempted to examine the marital status of the sample respondents. The following table describes the marital status of the Jasmine cultivators.

Table 4: Distribution of sample cultivators by marital status

S.No	Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Unmarried	17	5.67
2	Married	270	90.00
3	Divorced	13	4.33
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

From the above table it is known that 90 per cent of the sample respondents are married. 5.67 per cent of them are unmarried and the remaining 4.33 per cent of the sample respondents are divorced. Thus, from the above analysis it can be concluded that majority (90%) of the sample respondents are married.

Type of Family: The type of family is an important factor determining the level of yield and output. In the Indian context, it is common in agricultural occupation to engage the family members as field workers. They are called family labour. Majority of the family members who are engaged in agriculture happen to be the women folk. This reduces the employment of hired labour resulting in a reduction in production cost. In the case of joint family system, the availability of family labour is more than the nuclear family system. Hence, in the present paragraph it is attempted to examine the type of family of the sample Jasmine cultivators.

Table 5: Distribution of sample cultivators by type of family

S.No	Family Type	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Nuclear	203	67.67
2	Joint family	97	32.33
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table reveals that around 67.67 per cent of the sample respondents live under nuclear family system. The remaining 32.33 per cent of them adopted joint family system. Thus, from the above analysis it can be concluded that majority (67.67%) of the sample respondents live under nuclear family system.

Family Size: The number of members in the families of the farmers plays an important role in the cultivation of the Jasmine flowers. If the farmer's family size is larger, the availability of family labour will be higher and hence least dependent on hired labour. In the case of the families with lower number of members, the respondents have to depend on the hired labour for the cultivation activities. Hence, it becomes pertinent to

understand the number of members in the families of the sample respondents and in the present paragraph such an attempt is being made.

Table 6: Distribution of sample cultivators by number of members in the family

S.No	Family Size	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	Up to 2	17	5.67
2	3 – 5	159	53.00
3	6 – 8	103	34.33
4	9 and above	21	7.00
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 53 per cent of the sample respondents have 3 – 5 members in their families. 34.33 per cent of them have 6 – 8 members. There are 7 per cent of families who have 9 and above members. The remaining 5.67 per cent of the sample respondents have up to 2 members in their families. Thus, from the analysis it can be concluded that majority (53%) of the sample respondents' families have 3 - 5 members in their families.

Seasonal Cultivators / New Entrants: Some farmers have been engaged in the cultivation of Jasmine from generation to generation, but at the same time few cultivators who have been entered in the cultivation only recently.

Table 7: Distribution of sample cultivators by nature of involvement in agriculture

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Heredity	224	74.70
2	First generation farmer	76	25.30
	Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 74.70 per cent of the sample respondents viewed that because of the heredity they engage in this cultivation activity and the remaining 25.30 per cent of the respondents only engage in this cultivation as a first generation farmers. Thus, from the analysis it can be concluded that majority (74.70%) of the sample farmers involved in the cultivation are heredity farmers.

2. Multiple Regressions:

Multiple Regression is used to measure the proportion of variance two or more independent variables on the dependent variable

Table 8: Multiple Regression Analysis

Variable Code	Variable Name	Regression Coefficient	"p" Value	Significance
X1	Gender	.271	.171	Significant
X2	Age	-.010	.901	Significant
X3	Education	-.107	.088	Not Significant
X4	Marital Status	.425	.001	Significant
X5	Nature of Family	-.541	.002	Significant
X6	Family Size	-.039	.675	Not Significant

a. Dependent Variable: Cultivation

The result of the Multiple Regression reveals that out of the variables tested the variables such as the gender, age, marital status and nature of family significantly influence the cultivation of the jasmine flowers.

3. Chi-Square Test:

Chi-square test is used to find out the influence of various factors relating to the sample respondents (Independent variables) on the cultivation (Dependent variable). Null Hypotheses were formulated to find out whether social status factors influence the cultivation of the Jasmine flowers in Dindigul district. These null hypotheses were tested with the help of Chi-square test.

Ho: There is no association between age and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between age and cultivation problems.

Table 9: Association between age and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated Value	Df	Result
Age	15.507	111.44	8	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between age and cultivation problems.

Ho: There is no association between gender and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between gender and cultivation problems.

Table 10: Association between gender and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated Value	Df	Result
Gender	5.991	51.177	2	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between gender and cultivation problems.

Ho: There is no association between marital status and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between marital status and cultivation problems.

Table 11: Association between marital status and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated Value	Df	Result
Marital Status	9.488	93.96	4	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is significant association between marital status and cultivation problems.

Ho: There is no association between educational qualifications and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between educational qualifications and cultivation problems.

Table 12: Association between educational qualifications and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated Value	Df	Result
Educational Qualifications	15.507	132.51	8	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between educational qualifications and cultivation problems.

Ho: There is no association between nature of family and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between nature of family and cultivation problems.

Table 13: Association between nature of family and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated Value	Df	Result
Nature of family	5.991	69.51	2	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between nature of family and cultivation problems.

Ho: There is no association between family size and cultivation problems.

Ha: There is an association between family size and cultivation problems.

Table 14: Association between family size and cultivation problems

Variable	Table Value	Calculated value	Df	Result
Family size	12.592	127.90	6	Ho : Rejected

Source: Primary Data

Table value is less than the calculated value. So the null hypothesis (Ho) should be rejected i.e. there is a significant association between family size and cultivation problems.

The result of the Chi-square test indicates that social status factors (i.e. *Gender, Age, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Nature of Family, Family Size, and Seasoned cultivators / New entrants*) have significant association with the cultivation problems

9. Findings:

- ✓ It has been found that majority (50%) of the sample farmers are in the age group of 41 – 50 years.
- ✓ It has been observed that majority (72.67 %) of the sample farmers are male.
- ✓ It has been inferred that majority (38%) of the sample Jasmine cultivators are illiterates.
- ✓ It has been found that majority of the (90%) sample farmers are married.
- ✓ It has been found that majority of the sample families (67.67%) of the sample farmers have adopted nuclear family system.
- ✓ The study inferred that majority (74.70%) of the sample farmers involved in hereditary cultivation.
- ✓ It has been inferred that majority (53%) of the sample farmers have 3 - 5 members in their families.
- ✓ The result of the Multiple Regression reveals that out of the variables tested the variables such as the gender, age, marital status and nature of family significantly influence the cultivation of the jasmine flowers.
- ✓ The result of the Chi-square test indicates that social status factors (i.e. *Gender, Age, Marital Status, Educational Qualification, Nature of Family, Family Size, and Seasoned cultivators / New entrants*) have significant association with the cultivation problems

10. Conclusion:

The present study attempted to examine the role of social status of the cultivators in the cultivation of jasmine flowers. In simple words Gender, Age, Marital status, Educational qualification, Nature of family, Family size and seasoned.

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